

A Complete Off-line Sindhi Handwritten Text Recognition: A Survey

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Abstract: Artificial Intelligence is finding ways to make machines more intelligent and work like human being. Image processing, Natural language processing and Optical Character Recognition (OCR) are the active fields of computer vision, where the computers are made more versatile to understand, read and write natural human languages spoken around the world. Optical Characters Recognition (OCR) and Intelligent Characters Recognition (ICR) differ in recognizing printed and handwritten characters respectively. Intelligent Characters Recognition (ICR) is an active field in which handwritten characters are converted into editable text from the image, and remain the point of interest for researchers around the world. Many of the languages of the world possess their Intelligent Characters Recognition (ICR) or their ICR systems are in process. Latin scripts possess their ICR and are near to perfect whereas Arabic script and its adopting languages need more attention for the development of ICR systems. Sindhi language is a language having rich background and culture of more than 5000 years still lacks the ICR system. As there is no any handwritten recognition system for Sindhi Language, so there is no handwritten database is available for testing and training. Enhanced segmentation and feature extraction algorithms are needed which can fully suit with Sindhi script. An integrated handwritten system will be the output of this system in which handwritten text is recognized and editable text will be available for the further processing.

Keyword: Sindhi ICR, Computer Vision, Image Processing, Handwritten Text Recognition

I. INTRODUCTION

The research on Arabic language is reached at 70% perfection level where is the other language like Latin or Chinese reached at their perfection level. While Arabic Language possess many issues due to number of dots on letters. The work on Sindhi OCR or handwritten recognition is in its infancy and needs a lot of attention for the creation of OCR and ICR systems for Sindhi language. Sindhi Language has more characters than any other language which adopts Arabic script and very small work has been reported for Sindhi OCR system and found work for ICR is at its origin. A detailed discussion on the implementation challenges has been presented in Implementation and challenges[i]. A typical handwritten text recognition system contains four main stages such as pre-processing, segmentation, feature extraction and classification. A database of handwritten text images is required, so that testing and training of the system can be

performed. The literature review has been categorized according to the development stages of Sindhi Intelligent Characters Recognition (Sindhi ICR). Here we review those research papers which have more resemblance to Sindhi Language like Arabic, Deva Nagri, Pushto etc. Following literature review focuses on structures of ICR, such as Database Creation, Segmentation, Feature Extraction and Classification.

II. LITRATURE REVIEW

Database for Testing and Training:

Arabic Handwriting Database:

Ramdan and others created an Arabic Handwritten Database (AHDB) for the Arabic handwritten recognition. The database contains Arabic text images containing open vocabulary. The Arabic Database contains the different writing styles and segmented word and database also contains all forms of the Arabic characters such as first, last, middle and isolated. A total of five scholars having different age group and varying qualifications were asked to write the Arabic text line by using the pen of their own choice. The images of handwriting of different scholars were scanned by scanner using 300 dpi and stored in bit format. A total of 497 images were collected from different writers and each image contain the town names. Each image contains ground truth information about the author. The town name may contain up to three words and sub words. The writers were asked to write freely without any restriction. The database can be used for handwritten recognition. The handwritten database is freely available for testing and training[ii].

Text Image Database for Pashto:

Wahab created a Pashto text image database and presented a shape analysis of Pashto characters. The characteristics of Pashto script are discussed and the database importance and competitions are also the part of discussion. The database is containing the images, which were created synthetically and the ligatures are selected from a Pashto novel written by Muhammad Ajan Yar titled "Da Jwand ao Da Ceray". The selected ligatures were written in a software Aisha soft which uses Karor font style. The ligatures are written in software in four font sizes and converted into .bmp format and all of the images are of 100 * 100 pixel size. The last step is to convert these images into black and white binary format because these images were created as RGB. The four different writers participate in writing the ligatures, each writer wrote 1000 ligatures and total 4000 ligatures were collected. In result Pashto database contain 4000 ligatures. The database is tittle as Fast- NU Pashto image database. The database is available in University of Peshawar for testing and training[iii].

Reprocessing:

ICR Normalization Framework:

Abu-Ain with others proposed a handwritten cursive text normalization model which is based on detection and straightness of the base lines. Experiments are performed on Arabic script due the more languages adopting Arabic scripts. The directions features are extracted form a skeleton of a written sub words. The framework starts with the binarization of the image. For the detection of lines the words and sub words are processed separately to find out the baseline in a word and sub word. The body of sub word is kept and the dots as well as noise are removed by preprocessing techniques. Each sub word is passed through the horizontal projection histogram and the threshold is calculated. The baseline region is calculated with the help of threshold. The sub word is thinned to one pixel of width. The next step is to extract directional features from each sub word. Furthermore landmark labels are assigned to the connecting pixel and based on these landmark labels and the most number of labels will be considered as the baseline. Experiments performed on the subset of IFN/ENIT database[iv].

Handwritten character skeletonization:

Pervouchine proposed a novel method of stroke extraction approach for the character skeletonization. The approach is used in forensic handwritten documents. This method mimics the human perception of pen tip trajectory. The approach has the application in feature extraction algorithms which are sensitive to the location of skeleton curves. The algorithm comprises of three stages and uses greyscale image for experiments. The images are scanned from 150 dpi to 600 dpi for experiment. The skeleton of the character is based on junction points. Various subjects wrote a total of 150 images of grapheme “th” in handwriting [v].

Segmentation:

Sindhi Segmentation:

Shaikh et al proposed a segmentation algorithm which segments only six set of ligatures of Sindhi language based on height profile vector. A ligature of Sindhi script is used to segmented into characters. The ligature is thinned first and then applied segmentation algorithm. Horizontal projection is used to segment lines of text followed by base line detection. Ligatures are extracted and these ligatures are further segmented into characters. The baseline is detected using horizontal projection. The ligatures are found using connected components and these connected components are segmented into primary strokes. As the ligatures are already thinned so resultant segmented characters are in thinned binary image. The applied algorithm reported under and over segmentation problem[vi].

Amharic ICR:

Assabie and Bigun proposed an Amharic offline segmentation free approach working on word level recognition. The approach is recognizing handwritten Amharic script using Hidden Markov Chain Model. A total of 177 scholars written 307 pages, and all images containing total 10,932 words, The scholars were asked to write without any restriction. The data set is divided into training of 10 words and testing of 100 words. The dataset is also categorized into good and bad groups. By using Hidden Markov Chain Model the recognition rates are reported as 92% for 10 words. The 100 words recognition rate is 86%. The recognition rate is decreasing with the level of increasing samples, therefore 66% recognition rate is reported for 10,932. The rate is decreased

when the system is tested on poor quality documents and the recognition rate obtained for poor quality documents is 41% for all 10,932 documents[vii].

Bangla ICR:

Basu and others presented a novel technique for Bangla handwritten character segmentation and recognition system in which the characters are divided. The Bangla words are segmented using Matra hierarchy. The word images are segmented and individual parts are recognized through intelligent recognition combination decisions. A Bangla word segmentation is not an easy job due to its nature as many consecutive characters overlap each other. A two pass approach is employed with the certain segments of the word. The Multilayer Perceptron (MLP) has been selected for the classification of Bangla characters due to the generalization and learning capabilities. A feature extraction which is based on three topological features is designed for the complex character recognition. These three features are octant-centroid, longest run features and modified shadow features. A word is segmented in to three zones such as upper, middle and lower zones. The zone based recognition is performed which employs two pass classification. For the experiments a total of 12 databases are formed in which three databases are for upper, middle and lower zone of characters. One database is dedicated for CDM classifier and seven databases for group patterns and one database is created for cursive handwritten Bangla words. Middle zone database comprises of the basic segments or parts of the basic Bangla characters. These are the 300 basic samples for each 36 middle zone characters which constitute 10,800 samples in total. The database for CDM classifier contains 2,160 samples and these samples were divided into three categories such as basic character, digit and modified digit. The MLP recognition rate was reported as 72.06% using a single classifier[viii].

Sindhi and multi-script database:

Amin presented a survey of techniques during the two decades of the printed and handwritten character recognition research. This paper focuses on the segmentation approaches. The current status of Arabic printed and handwritten recognition is also discussed in paper. The Arabic character recognition process including word segmentation, feature extraction and recognition are discussed in detail by explaining the various approaches followed by various researchers. The handwritten recognition is classified as the open area of research, where cursive nature of various languages and segmentation peculiarities of Arabic script discussed. The result comparison of handwritten recognition has been justified as a difficult task because there is no standard database for Arabic characters is available and the available systems are tested on a small database. The results of handwritten recognition algorithms by various researchers are not included because the experiments are performed on small and individual databases. The handwritten character recognition is classified in this paper as the potential area of research[ix].

Feature Extraction:

Writer identification for Arabic Handwriting:

Newell and Griffin proposed a writer identification system based on Delta encoding and oriented Basic Image Features (oBIF). The writer style can be encoded and identified by finding out the deviation from the mean encoding of group of writers. The process starts by encoding the Arabic characters into oBIF for two sizes. By using Derivative-of-Gaussian (DtG) filters each

point is classified into seven symmetries. These values are grouped at different sizes. The next step is removing flat values, counting or remaining values, forming histogram and normalization. The experiments are performed on IAM database. The result of 99% performance is reported when tested on 300 subjects of IAM database. The delta encoding is a performance increasing factor[x].

Pashto Recognition using SIFT features

Ahmad proposed a segmentation free Pashto OCR system using Scale-invariant feature transform (SIFT) features. The SIFT descriptor based holistic framework is claimed to be used for any other cursive language. The research presents some of the characteristics of Pashto script and extraction of features from Pashto words as the approach is a word based recognition. The database used for the experiments is created by Wahab et al. (2009) on OCR at University of Peshawar. This paper also presents some repetition of the Wahab et al. (2009) database and explains the four additional features added to the database and now this database contains 8000 images of 1000 unique ligatures. MATLAB is used for the extraction of SIFT features. Three experiments are discussed by using SIFT and PCA. The recognition rate of 8000 Pashto ligatures is 74% by using features extracted only 1000 ligatures. The authors report that SIFT features outperform PCA technique when working with scaling size variation and rotation[xi].

Handwritten Numeral Recognition:

Yang and others discussed feature extraction method using integrated neural network by using character feature extraction for handwritten numeral recognition. The backpropagation network can be improved by activation function, initialization and method based on feature extraction. The paper presented the theory of classifier reliability identification and handwritten digits are chosen for the testing of its extension. It is claimed that this method requires less computation and simple in application and can be used as the one of the additional classifier when using integrated neural networks and can improve the accuracy of handwritten digit recognition[xii].

Devanagari Handwritten Shape Features:

Mukherji and Rege proposed fuzzy logic and shape based recognition system for isolated Devanagari characters. The character is applied thinning algorithm to find skeletonized image which is segmented into basic strokes using structural features. These structural features are endpoints, junction points and cross points. A new approach Average Compressed Direction Code (ACDC) is used to encode segments of character. The segment strokes are classified in one of the groups such as slanted line, vertical and horizontal strokes. Knowledge grammar is used to recognize the characters using various properties such as stroke shapes, column coordinates, mean row and relative strength. The characters are also classified by using a tree classifier. The average recognition rate is 86.4% achieved by the system[xiii].

Arabic ICR using Structural and Syntactic Pattern Attributes:

Parvez and Mahmoud proposed an Arabic handwritten recognition system based on structural and syntactic pattern attributes. Several algorithms are novel as claimed by the research. The characteristics of Arabic language are explained. The lines and words are extracted from a paper then the dots are removed. After removing dots, the adaptive algorithm is applied which corrects the various angles of component hence the skewness is corrected. The baseline is detected with the help of

components. Second model system is proposed for the Arabic character recognition offline. The first model training contains approximation contours of characters, fuzzy attributed function and model steps. The recognition contains multiple steps and starts with Segmentation in which Parts of Arabic Words (PAWs) are segmented with the approximation of contours. These PAWs are further segmented and then the next step is to identify the characters in PAWs. The system identifies base shapes of the characters first and then the dots are recognized. The recognized dots are assigned to the recognized base shape. The experiments are performed on IFN/ENIT database. The nearest neighbor is selected for the classification of characters which produces the 79.58% of accuracy for the system[xiv].

Classification:

Chinese / Japanese ICR:

Zhu and Nakagawa proposed a classification approach for online Chinese and Japanese handwritten recognition. A course classifier is used to increase the speed of recognition the candidates for recognition are reduced. This reduced candidate set is used by fine classifier. A fine classifier is used along with geometric context module and Segmentation module. Coarse classifier contains the preprocessing and feature extraction stages followed by basic character recognizers. A total of 243 basic classifiers were created. These classifiers possess various accuracies and classification costs. The original time of recognition is reduced and only one stage are used while maintaining the recognition rates[xv].

Handwritten Digit recognition:

Bouchain discussed gradient based and convolutional neural network. A basic network overview is discussed followed by convolutional networks. The gradient based learning and multi-layer perceptron is also discussed. Testing and training of the database contains 5,000 handwritten digits. The digits used as input image are normalized to the center. The testing obtained 0.95% of error rate which was reduced more when the network was trained with distorted samples of digits. The results are also tested with multilayer perceptron which produced error rate of 4.5% by using only one hidden layer. The multilayer perceptron produced 3.05% error rate when it was tested with two hidden layers. The first hidden layer contained 300 neurons and the second layer contains 100 neurons. When the number of neurons increased as 1000 neurons in first hidden layer and 150 neurons in the second hidden layer and then the error rate was reduced to 2.45%. The neural network application leNet-5 was developed and it has a good performance[xvi].

English ICR using Neural Network (NN):

Ganapathy and Liew proposed a system for English handwritten recognition system trained on multi-scale neural network. The subjects wrote English characters on a white paper using black marker Artline70. A total of 10 varying shaped characters were prepared for training and testing. These shapes were prepared for 26 capital letters of English alphabet and ten digits. Digital camera Canon IXUS 40 used to scan the images for input. These images used for generating input vectors to be used as input layer of backpropagation neural network. The output layer contains 36 neurons, 26 for letters and 10 for numerals. Hidden layer contains 1500 neurons selected after experimentation. A multi-scale approach is used for training of the network and a separate dataset was prepared to test the network. The images are prepared

in $20 * 28$, $10 * 15$ and $5 * 7$, sizes of the pixels and the network will become slow if the resolution of the input images are increased due to the more calculations for the network. The system produces recognition accuracy of 85% for English letters[xv].

Bangla Handwritten Numeral recognition:

Wen and He proposed a novel classification for Bangla handwritten numeral recognition. A combination of two classifiers, Bayesian discriminant and kernel is used to classify the sample class distribution. The experiments contain 45,000 of numerals and the data was collected from Dhaka post office automatic letter sorting machine. A randomly selected 30,000 numerals were used as training set whereas the remaining used for testing. The experiments are performed on a 2GB RAM installed Windows XP based computer running 1.8 GHz CPU. Eight classifiers are used for the sake of comparison of results and PCA for the feature extraction. The experiments performed on UCI (Blake, Keogh, & Merz, 1998) containing 5630 samples and MNIST databases. The data distribution of the UCI database is randomly produced and 300 samples were used for training and rest for testing. The sample of numeral image was resized to $32 * 32$ pixel size. The MNIST database contains 60,000 of numerals images and 10,000 were selected for training. The training images were resized to $28 * 28$ pixel size and normalized to center. The proposed algorithm applied on original MNIST database and the error rate achieved is 1.8%. Which is a good performance and simple to implement even it is not the best as the best classifier in the market (Lecun et al., 1995; Lecun, Bottou, Bengio, & Haffner, 1998) is performing with 0.95% of error rate[xvi].

Tamil ICR:

Hewavitharana and Fernando proposed a two stage classifier for the recognition of Tamil handwritten word. The process involves combination of statistical and structural approaches and Tamil language properties are also discussed. The experimental section is divided into five major stages. The first stage is data collection in which different A4 papers used to collect data from different writers and collected data is passed through processing stage. In preprocessing the global threshold was used to binarize the image, noise elimination and extract the writing. For the line structural properties are used and the histogram is used to segment text lines and words. The characters are segmented and then the following stage is preliminary classification. The features are extracted using bilinear interpolation approach which resizes the input image into $32 * 32$. The classification uses interval estimation with the help of statistical approach. The character is classified in one of the pre-classify groups called ascending, core and descending. The other classifier is used to further classify the characters which is considered as actual recognition. A total of 1,000 images were used for training whereas 800 used for testing the data and the testing data also contained some of the samples used for training. The recognition rate is obtained in both classifiers. The actual or final classification produces the recognition rate of 80% whereas the first classifier which categorize into three categories has achieved 97% of recognition rate. On an experiment of 50 text lines all characters available are classified correctly and system achieved 99% of segmentation accuracy hence producing the pre-classification error rate of 1% [xvii].

Integrated ICR/OCR Systems: State of the Art

Sindhi OCR using NN:

Nizamani and Janjua projected an OCR for Sindhi isolated characters. The system works for isolated Sindhi characters drawn using mouse on a drawing panel. The system contains four steps namely input normalization, feature extraction, classification and recognition. The user draws a Sindhi character using mouse and the character is normalized to a fixed size and then features are extracted from this character. The simple feature algorithm makes use of $20 * 20$ template in which white spaces are skipped. The feature vector is used as an input to a backpropagation neural network which recognizes the isolated characters. The data is given in a list box. The recognition network follows SOM topology containing two layers of nodes. $20 * 20$ lattice is used and 400 total of neurons are calculated. No recognition rate is reported in this research[xviii].

Offline handwriting Recognition by NN:

Zamora-Martinez and others discussed problems of continuous unconstrained handwritten recognition and proposed language decoding model based on Hidden Markov Chain Model, bidirectional long short term memory (BLSTM) neural network and the combination of both. A subset of IAM handwritten database version 3.0 was created and used for experiments. The results are compared with other reference systems and a lower error rate is reported. The reference models are reported different compared to proposed system in many parameters. Combined system based on HMM and ANN proved better performer on larger vocabularies compared to BLSTM network. Combined approach also proved good performer with lower error rate compared to reference systems. Final rate for word error is reported as 16.1% is reported and claimed a reduction of 38% compared the best previous published work. A 25% reduction is achieved compared to best published reference system previously. Character error rate is reported to 8% [xix].

Arabic Text Recognition:

Sarfraz proposed an Arabic text recognition system that works offline. The paper discusses characteristics of Arabic script including the changing form property of Arabic characters when connected to other characters. The typical OCR system starts with image acquisition followed by preprocessing and segmentation. Artificial neural network is proposed for classification. The OCR system is created in Java for Naskh font. The system works for one font and multiple sizes. Input images used are 200 in number and the system was tested with various Naskh font characters which produces 73% of recognition rate. The experiments were performed on system running Pentium III (500 MHz) using JDK 1.4.1[xx].

Online Isolate Arabic Intelligent Characters Recognition (Arabic ICR):

Al-Taani and Al-Haj proposed an offline approach to recognize isolated handwritten Arabic characters. The approach performs experiment online with isolated Arabic characters and can be adopted to a tablet PC. The system is recognizing character strokes by recording the x and y coordinate locations of the pixels. To separate and understand mouse click is used to recognize a stroke for the characters. Then, the characters are recorded into number of segments and after getting input the character is stored in an image and the image is divided into $5 * 5$ segments. These segments are used to extract features from the image. A character is classified according to the group of four base shapes and classifier performs the job. Loop inside the shape

of the character is used as a feature. Learning by a decision tree is the basic recognizer for the input characters. A Single character is written five times so that the data collection of the single character may be available in many shapes. A total of ten writers wrote a letter five times which means a single letter was written 50 times. Experiments used 1400 characters and recognition rate 75.3% is reported. Some of the characters which have sharp edge are recognized at lower rate of 48.8% and if these characters are replaced from the experimental data then the system recognizes the characters at 85.3%. The recognition rate of each character of isolated characters are also presented[xxi].

English ICR by NN:

Saha and Som discussed an English handwritten recognition system using neural network. The system also uses Euclidean distance for the improvement of accuracy for recognition. The characters are normalized to a box and the character must touch all of the sides of the box. The box containing a character is then resized to 100 * 100 resolution. A single character having total of 10 shapes and the neural network will generate the weights for every character. The character is given to neural network and then the initialized weights are changed by the network and new weights are generated. The characters are recognized according to the highest weight carrying character. Some of the characters produce mismatching because these characters share a part of the character shape with each other. To solve this problem of mismatching, the Euclidean distance was used so that mismatching problems cannot occur. The research reported that experiments were performed on large database and results are quite high but there is no any experiments given in this research[xxii].

Symbol Recognition:

Santosh proposed an electrical wiring symbol recognition system based on spatio-structural descriptors. These descriptor are extracted from the elementary parts of vocabulary. The vocabulary is a group of elements in symbols such as corner or circles. The process starts by description of visual vocabulary. Then, the spatial relations are calculated in the next step. Attributional Relation Graph (ARG) is developed by using the visual vocabulary and spatial relations calculated in the previous step. In ARG the edges are labelled by using numerical equations. After the symbols are represented through ARG the next stage is the symbol recognition. The two ARGs are compared and the result score is purely calculated from matching the two ARGs. The order of similarity will help to generate database rankings. For performing experiments all of the symbols are labelled and ground truth were formatted. The symbols are recognized and a ranking list is generated. A global signal based descriptors are created so that the recognition method can be compared with other approaches. The experiments were also performed to compare the approach with other two pixel based approaches which are specially designed for symbol namely Kernel density matching (KDM) (Zhang et al., 2006) and statistical integration of histogram array (SIHA) (Yang,2005). The running time has also been compared with other approaches. Experiments are performed on LINUX platform running 7.8.0 version of MATLAB[xxiii].

Chinese ICR using Locality alignment:

Tao and others discussed retrieval of discriminative information for Chinese handwritten recognition and justified as very important for the performance increase. A theoretical

investigation presented is a good tool to better estimate the robustness of KLDA. A subspace learning algorithm based on discriminative locality alignment (DLA) is used to find out the subspace by increasing trace between the class and decreasing trace within the class in scatter matrix. DLA contains three stages in which the first is linear discriminant analysis, the second stage is Discriminative locality alignment and the last stage is Part optimization. Two levels of classifications have been used for retrieval of alignment. A performance increasing for generating similar character set Static candidate generation (SCG) has been used. DLA and KDLA are reported as the best performer consistently on similar Chinese character recognition and are robust and no any single matrix problem reported so far. The DLA and KDLA are best suited to the real world application[xxiii].

Other Sindhi Related Research Work

Sindhi Overview:

Sindhi OCR challenges

Hakro and discussed a detailed analysis of challenges in implementation of Sindhi OCR. The paper discusses Sindhi script characteristic pertaining OCR creation for Sindhi OCR. The bidirectional style of writing and multiple writing systems in use are also discussed. The script complexities imposed by Sindhi script are presented in detail such as cursiveness, Number of characters, character similarity, placement of dots, number of dots, orientation of dots, shape groups available in Sindhi script and same base shape used for multiple characters without changing the base shape. Context sensitivity is also considered as the potential challenge for implementation of OCR because characters become different in shape when they are connected different shapes. Some of the overall challenges faced by OCR researchers are also presented such as skew, noise, font size and Sindhi ligatures. A summary of challenges is also included in the last[xxiv].

Sindhi related script recognition:

Hakro presented the problems of recognition and approaches followed by most of the researchers for Sindhi and its related languages that adopt Arabic scripts. The Latin and Chinese OCRs are nearly in the perfection border and Arabic script is also followed by most of the researchers, whereas the languages that use Arabic characters need more attention as their OCR research is at starting point. The paper presents a rich historical background of Sindhi language. The next section discusses the history of OCR and OCR techniques. The paper also presented OCR elements in detail in which the steps of OCR development are discussed along with the approaches followed by various researchers around the world for their research for various languages. The problems are correlated with Sindhi script and other languages that adopt Arabic script[i].

Problem Statement:

- Most of the languages are enriched with their OCR and ICR systems or they are in the development process but very little work has been done in Sindhi script. So there is a need to investigate in-depth challenges and difficulties posed by Sindhi script for the development of handwritten text recognition system.
- As there is no Sindhi ICR/handwritten recognition system, so there is no data set available for training and testing. That's

why a new database for handwritten characters recognition is required.

- The ICR systems are traditionally reported on segmentation free approach which limits the use of handwritten recognition. As this approach is limited and it recognizes only specific ligatures or words, therefore in order to recognize any ligatures and words of Sindhi ICR there is a need of suitable segmentation technique for handwritten Sindhi text to recognize written words in Sindhi script.
- Sindhi script possesses a total of 52 characters and these characters change their shape depending upon the use in sentence, and also different numbers of dots with different positions, so there is a need for suitable feature extraction technique which fully suits for the representation of Sindhi characters.
- As there is no complete Sindhi ICR, so there is a need a complete Sindhi ICR system which recognizes unlimited ligatures or words for Sindhi script.

Specific objectives of research

- To investigate in-depth difficulties and peculiarities for the development of offline Sindhi intelligent characters recognition system.
- To create a scalable handwritten database for Sindhi script that can be easily accessed and used by other researchers.
- To enhance segmentation technique for Sindhi ICR.
- To enhance feature extraction technique that fully suits with Sindhi ICR.
- To classify and recognize Sindhi characters using machine learning technique.
- To integrate above approaches and develop a complete system for Sindhi ICR.

III. MATERIALS AND METHODOLOGY

Methodology of research is given bellow in the flow chart:

2.4.1 Phases for Offline Sindhi Intelligent Characters Recognition (ICR):

Figure 1: Stages of offline Sindhi Intelligent Characters Recognition System

Phase 1: Analyzing Peculiarities:

Handwritten recognition needs a considerable amount of time to understand the peculiarities available in Sindhi alphabet and difficulties posed by the script. At this stage a thorough and deep investigation will be done for the difficulties and challenges in the process of handwritten recognition system.

Phase 2: Data Collection:

As there is no handwritten recognition system so there is no any database for the Sindhi script. For the creation of database we try to create a database for handwritten Sindhi text. For this purpose, a comprehensive database for handwritten will be created in which many of the subjects will be the target to write Sindhi text on prescribed forms. At this stage the handwriting of many users will be collected so that a significant size of the database can be mapped. The subject may write with different writing styles. They may write the name of countries, name of boys and girls and so on. Subject may be categorized according to their qualifications or may be with different writing expertise or styles.

Phase 3: Handwritten Database Creation:

At this stage the collected forms and writings of various subjects will be passed through some experiments and the database for handwritten Sindhi text will be created so that the ICR processes can be implemented. The recognition system requires the input image which are written by various users. For this purpose a comprehensive database will be created for handwritten Sindhi script. Here preprocessing is also done to remove the some noise and unnecessary dots. In the preprocessing stages the boundaries and lines are corrected to make the data normalized for further processing.

Phase 4: Text Image Segmentation:

The segmentation is the main step of ICR in which the handwritten text, ligatures or words are segmented to their constitute characters. These characters are used as input to the next level of ICR called feature extraction.

Phase 5: Feature Extraction:

After segmenting the characters from lines, words, ligatures and characters are represented in a vector form so that a character can be identified and recognized. Various algorithms are available to find a suitable algorithm that can fully suit with the Sindhi characters.

Phase 6: Classification / Recognition:

The characters are segmented and represented in a vector form which will be used in a trained classifier so that a character may be recognized. Here classifier will check the character and mates with the learned characters and on successful matching a character is called recognized.

Phase 7: Editable Text:

On successful matching of the classifier a code is generated and this code is then decoded and the number is checked with the corresponding character Unicode. Newly found Unicode character is then sent to a Unicode supported text editor where this text can be edited. The output of the OCR and ICR are presented in Unicode text editor where they can be easily edited.

Phase 8: Complete ICR:

The above processes and approaches are combined and integrated to an application, where with the help of easy interface, the handwritten script is converted into editable text so that can be used in other applications and can be edited.

Data Collection:

- Creating forms

The forms will be created so that these forms will be given to various writers so that they can write Sindhi script on the forms. The forms will be prepared by keeping in view for the all aspects for handwriting recognition. The forms will be written in constrained and unconstrained format.

- **Writing of forms**

The subjects belong to various geography, demography, age, gender and so on. Forms will be presented to the writers. Than written forms will be collected.

- **Collection of forms and basic analysis**

The written forms collected and basic analysis techniques will be applied so that we can track record of writing of contents of the forms, subject and other information can be stored and tracked.

- **Creation of Database**

A comprehensive database will be created after performing basic image processing approaches so that the database can meet the criteria of a standard database for Sindhi script.

IV. RESULTS, SCOPE & LIMITATION

Scope & Limitation:

The research is focused on 2D images handwritten by at least 500 subjects in Sindhi language. The written material will be collected and will be used as input. The handwritten documents in Sindhi will be scanned and used to recognize only Sindhi script. The output will be in the form of editable text as Unicode characters that can be edited on any text editor supporting Unicode.

Expected Research Results:

The expected outcomes of this research are as follows:

- A comprehensive text image database for the handwritten recognition will be created so that Sindhi script and other languages that adopt Arabic script may use for training and testing of their recognition systems.
- An enhanced segmentation algorithm will be the output of this research so that recognition rate can be increased.
- An enhanced Feature extraction will be the output of this research so that handwritten Sindhi characters can be presented in suitable way.
- An integrated handwritten recognition system incorporating above enhanced approaches will be produced so that handwritten Sindhi characters can be recognized with higher recognition rate.
- An in-depth Analysis of the problems during the implementation of Sindhi intelligent character recognition will be the output of this research.

A complete integrated handwritten recognition system will incorporate above enhanced approaches. Finally, a handwritten Sindhi character system can recognize the characters and helps to increase the accuracy rate.

Research Benefits:

Most of the languages are enriched with handwritten recognition systems. The languages having fewer speakers are also having a good computing support. Sindhi language is a rich language and we need more computing on Sindhi language. With the help of Sindhi handwritten language recognition support the language can be ranked with other languages which are having ICR

systems. The output of this research is a complete working software for the handwritten recognition system for ICR.

Outputs:

- The dataset of handwritten Sindhi language characters will be produced.
- An application for offline handwritten text recognition for Sindhi language will be developed.

Utilization of results:

- Developed dataset can be used by the research community for the training of newly developed systems for handwritten Sindhi text recognition.
- This system will lead to digitize the old handwritten books.
- Resultant system can be used to recognize offline handwritten text for Sindhi language.
- The resultant analysis of the challenges and difficulties will help to design and improve the quality of future research in Sindhi language.

V. CONCLUSION

In-depth analysis of Sindhi ICR System implementation and its challenges have been presented along-with general problems faced during the implementation of Sindhi ICR System. Various existing handwritten text image databases have been analyzed and a new scale-able Sindhi Text image database has been created so that Sindhi handwritten text images can be tested and trained. After the segmentation process the database has been created. Database contains segmented Sindhi words. Database also contains the line and column segmented data as well. Database comprises of images. This Sindhi text based images will be used for the testing and training of Sindhi characters recognition ICR Sindhi text image database may be extended in future by collecting the more samples from the users This database will be used for the training and testing purpose for other languages which possess the same characteristics of Sindhi Language. In future the database will be available online for testing and training for other researchers. The name for the database will be suggested in future when the database size may reach at some extent level. A form was created after various experiments and final version of forms were filled by various subjects. The written forms were collected and preprocessed using image processing techniques. The images of the filled forms were segmented into lines, lines into words and then stored into database for testing and training purpose. This database can be used by researchers of Sindhi language as well as the researchers of other languages possessing the same characters as like Sindhi script.

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